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Rahim Thawer - Queer Mental Health Media Archive

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Abstract

Clinical discussion on anti-racism work in queer contexts, examining how unconscious biases operate in therapeutic and community settings. Addresses moving from passive non-racism to active anti-racism in mental health practice. Provides frameworks for recognizing and addressing racial dynamics within LGBTQ+ communities and clinical work, supporting collective liberation through conscious anti-oppressive practice.

Keywords

intersectionality, cultural competence, psychodynamic

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